

Reactivity of some chloro diphenyltin(IV) dithiophosphates towards Lewis bases

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Abstract : The interactions of chloro diphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphates, $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)\{S(S)P(OR)_2\}]$ and $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)\{S(S)POGQ\}]$, (R = C_2H_5 ; G = $-CH_2C(H)-CH_3$ and $-CH_2(CH_2)_3CH_2-$) with various N-, O- and S-donor Lewis bases have yielded new stable molecular adducts. The complexes have been characterized by IR, 1H and ^{31}P NMR spectra. The results suggest the presence of five- and six-coordinated tin atom in case of unidentate and bidentate Lewis bases respectively.

Keywords : Organotin(IV) compounds, dithiophosphates, Lewis base.

Organotin compound have been subject of interest for some time because of biometrical and commercial application¹. To aid in understanding their biochemical application, it was felt that the coordination chemistry of tin(IV) towards O-, S- and N-containing ligand required further exploration. In continuation of our earlier work on the synthesis and reactivity of organometal *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate². We now examined the reactivity of chloro diphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-diethyl/alkylene dithiophosphates, with several Lewis bases such as, dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO), dimethyl formamide (DMF), 2,6-lutidine *N*-oxide (2,6-lut-O), pyridine-*N*-oxide (Py-O), dimethyl acetamide (DMA), antipyrine (Ap), thiourea (Tu), tetramethylthiuram disulphide (Me_4tds), 1,10-phenanthroline (*o*-phen) and 2,2'-bipyridyl (2,2'-bipy).

Results and discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) correspond to 1 : 1 (metal dtp : base) stoichiometry. The adducts are crystalline solid, thermally stable at room temperature and unaffected by atmospheric oxygen and moisture. These are soluble in common organic solvents. The adducts are non-conducting in DMSO ($2.34-3.62 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$), indicate absence of ionic species in solution.

IR spectra : The bands due to the $\nu(P)-O-C$, $\nu P-O-(C)$ and $\nu P-S$ identified at 1016 ± 2 , 960 ± 2 , 515 ± 2 (diethyl dtp) and at 1020 ± 4 , 972 ± 2 , $520 \pm 2 cm^{-1}$ (alkylene dtp) respectively in the parent chloro diphenyltin *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate³ shifted to higher wave number and appeared at 1034 ± 5 , 965 ± 2 , $532 \pm 6 cm^{-1}$ (dialkyl dtp) and at 1035 ± 5 , 974 ± 4 , $540 \pm$

$10 cm^{-1}$ (alkylene dtp) respectively in the IR spectra of the adducts. The band due to $\nu P=S$ present in chloro diphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphates at 650 ± 2 (dialkyl dtp) and at 691 ± 2 (alkylene dtp) have consistently been observed in the almost same region in the molecular adducts. The absorption due to $\nu Sn-S$ remains unaffected and appeared at 418 ± 2 (Ref. 4). The absorption due to (Sn-Ph) remains almost unaffected and appears in the region $440-450 cm^{-1}$ (Refs. 2, 5).

Sulphur donors : In the spectra of the sulphur donor ligand such as Me_4tds and Tu, the $\nu C=S$ appearing at 988 and $1090 cm^{-1}$ respectively shift to lower wave number on coordination and appears at 965 and $1050 cm^{-1}$ respectively in the adducts. These observations indicate coordination through S atom of the linear thiuram disulphide chain in case of Me_4tds and $Sn \leftarrow S$ bonding⁵ in the case of thiourea.

Oxygen donors : A considerable shift of $\nu C=O$ stretching mode from $1649 \pm 17 cm^{-1}$ in various free bases to a lower frequency $1624 \pm 4 cm^{-1}$ in case of the adducts, indicates coordination through the carbonyl oxygen⁵. Absorptions of strong intensity for $\nu S=O$ and $\nu N=O$ (Ref. 5) at 1045 and $1245 cm^{-1}$ respectively in the spectra of the free ligand undergo distinct negative shifts on complexation. The corresponding absorption in the spectra of the adducts appear at 990 ± 4 and $1220 \pm 5 cm^{-1}$, suggesting coordination from oxygen atom of the bases. In the far IR spectra a band at $344 \pm 4 cm^{-1}$ is assigned to $\nu Sn \leftarrow O$ stretching mode of vibration.

Nitrogen donors : The $\nu C=N$ modes appearing at 1569

Note

Table 1. Analytical data of $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)\{S(S)P(OR)_2\}].L$ and $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)\{S(S) \text{ POGO} \}].L$

Sl. no.	L	M.p. (°C)	G = -CH ₂ C(H)CH ₃		M.p. (°C)	G = -CH ₂ (CH ₂) ₃ CH ₂		M.p. (°C)	R = -CH ₂ CH ₃	
			Found (Calcd.) %			Found (Calcd.) %			Found (Calcd.) %	
			Sn	S		Sn	S		Sn	S
1.	2,6-lut-O	230	17.94 (17.96)	9.66 (9.68)	250*	18.86 (18.88)	10.15 (10.17)	254*	19.27 (19.26)	10.41 (10.38)
2.	DMA	200*	19.02 (19.00)	10.26 (10.24)	155	20.02 (20.04)	10.77 (10.80)	230*	20.45 (20.46)	11.00 (11.03)
3.	DMF	232	19.42 (19.43)	10.45 (10.47)	216	20.62 (20.59)	11.05 (11.06)	250*	20.94 (20.96)	11.28 (11.30)
4.	Ap	>260	16.32 (16.35)	8.80 (8.81)	160	16.99 (16.97)	9.12 (9.15)	220*	17.40 (17.42)	9.37 (9.39)
5.	Tu	200	19.32 (19.34)	15.66 (15.64)	240	20.47 (20.49)	16.50 (16.52)	140	20.89 (20.86)	16.88 (16.87)
6.	Py-O	120	17.06 (17.04)	9.17 (9.18)	140	19.66 (19.65)	10.57 (10.59)	190*	19.99 (20.05)	10.82 (10.80)
7.	Me ₄ tds	180	15.22 (15.25)	24.70 (24.67)	160	15.90 (15.92)	25.79 (25.75)	128	16.14 (16.17)	26.15 (26.17)
8.	DMSO	220	19.30 (19.27)	15.58 (15.59)	228	20.12 (20.14)	16.28 (16.29)	240*	20.81 (20.78)	16.77 (16.80)
9.	<i>o</i> -Phen	224*	16.10 (16.13)	8.15 (8.17)	198	16.91 (16.88)	9.13 (9.10)	80	17.16 (17.16)	9.24 (9.26)
10.	2,2-Bipy	230	16.94 (16.96)	9.50 (9.47)	242	17.80 (17.79)	9.57 (9.59)	190*	18.27 (18.28)	9.88 (9.85)

*decomp. pt.

$\pm 9 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in free *o*-phen and 2,2'-bipy undergo positive shifts and are located at $1587 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the corresponding adducts suggesting the presence of coordinated bases⁶. In the far IR spectra ν_{Sn-N} is identified at 386 cm^{-1} , which is close to a previous report⁵.

¹H NMR spectra : In the ¹H NMR spectra of parent $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)\{S(S)P(OCH_2CH_3)_2\}]$, the C₆H₅-Sn, O-CH₂ and CH₃ signals appear at δ 7.88–7.41 (m), 4.02–3.94 (m) and 1.27–1.22 (t) ppm respectively³ where as in the ¹H NMR spectra of $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)\{S(S)P(OCH_2CH_3)_2\}].L$. DMSO, the characteristic proton signals due to aryl group of Lewis acid are almost unaffected and appear at δ 7.90–7.41 ppm as multiplets whereas, the signals due to (O-CH₂) and (CH₃) shifts to high field and appear at δ 4.01–3.86 ppm and 1.10–0.90 ppm respectively indicating considerable drift of electrons from Lewis base to the metal atom. The ¹H NMR spectra of $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)\{S(S)PO(CH_2CH_3)_2\}].L$.DMSO shows a singlet at δ 2.66 ppm which is attributed to methyl protons of Lewis base. The positions and integrations of the peaks are consistent with the proposed stoichiometry of the adducts.

³¹P NMR spectra : In the ³¹P NMR spectrum of parent $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)S(S)P(OCH_2CH_3)_2]$, a single peak is observed at δ 109.77 ppm³. However, the ³¹P NMR spectrum of $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)S(S)P(OCH_2CH_3)_2].DMA$ show shielding of the phosphorus atom to the extent of about δ 2.2 ppm from the parent chloro diphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-diethyl dithiophosphate and a peak at δ 107.57 ppm is observed. The shielding of the phosphorus atom in molecular adducts supports the results obtained from IR and ¹H NMR spectra.

On the basis of foregoing discussion and support from the previous work^{5,6}, it is proposed that tin atom in the molecular adducts $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)\{S(S)P(OCH_2CH_3)_2\}].L$ and $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)\{S(S) \text{ POGO} \}].L$, is 5-coordinated in the case of L = unidentate base while 6-coordinated in L = bidentate base. The following tentative structures are shown below

where, L = DMSO, DMF, 2,6-lut-O, Py-O, DMA, Ap, Tu and Me₄tds; L' = *o*-phen and 2,2'-bipy.

Experimental

$[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)\{S(S)POCH_2C(H)OCH_3\}]$, $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)\{S(S)P(OCH_2CH_3)_2\}]$ and $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(Cl)POCH_2(CH_2)_3CH_2O]$ were synthesized as earlier³. The Lewis bases were obtained from B.D.H. and Aldrich Chemical Co., USA and were used without purification. Solvents were dried as reported earlier⁷. Sulphur was estimated as BaSO₄ and Sn was estimated as SnO₂⁸. The molar conductance of the compounds were measured using a dip-type conductivity cell on a Decible conductivity meter model DC 610 in anhydrous DMSO. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer model 883 in the region 4000–200 cm⁻¹ in KBr and CsI (in few cases) and Shimadzu 8201 PC FTIR spectrophotometer in the region 4000–400 cm⁻¹ in KBr. ¹H and ³¹P NMR spectra were recorded at 300 MHz and 121.5 MHz on a Bruker DRX-300 FT NMR spectrophotometer in CH₃OH-*d*₄ using TMS (as internal standard) and H₃PO₄ (as an external standard) respectively.

Preparation of adducts : The molecular adducts were prepared by the direct interaction of Lewis bases with chloro diphenyltin(IV) *O,O'*-diethyl/alkylene dithiophosphate in suitable solvent. In a representative experiment, a solution of tetramethylthiuram disulphide (0.240 g, 0.001 mol) in methanol (10 mL) was added dropwise to a solution of chloro diphenyltin diethyl dithiophosphate (0.493 g, 0.001 mol) in same solvent (10 mL). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for ~4 h. The

excess solvent was distilled off and the desired product was obtained by adding diethyl ether. The precipitate was filtered, washed several times with diethyl ether and dried over P₂O₅ *in vacuo*.

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